

Narrative Report Round XI (October 2022 - March 2023)

Applicant organisation details

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Stream (National, Regional):	Regional

Please provide a brief description of your project/activities. What activities were you able to carry out with this grant?

From October 2022 to March 2023, we engaged in various activities concerning the theme. Initially we mapped the parliamentarians from Portugal and Spain and the respective observers so that we could send out the invitations.

We held fortnightly meetings with the InterAgency Institute team involved in Round XI to work on the strategy for approaching parliamentarians and on the preparation of materials so that we could situate the guests with the debate and campaign proposals.

The e-mails were triggered three times, obeying the response time. Our original proposal was to work with parliamentarians from Portugal and Spain in an online debate. Faced with the lack of responses from Portugal, both from parliamentarians and observers, we decided to continue with the proposal to hold a debate valuing what we call Iberophony and having representations in both languages. In this sense, we established contact with the Cape Verde parliament, which promptly responded by appointing a parliamentarian.

We emphasize that the change did not harm the objective of the debate, being even more effective by including a country from the Global South and thus raising awareness and expanding the debate of the campaign, since Cape Verde is not yet a member.

We held meetings with Prof Dr Danielle Ayres Jacon Pinto and with the Center for African Studies for Development and Innovation (CEADI), from Brazil and Cape Verde respectively, so that they could be our observers. I would like to point out that Prof Danielle Ayres is a professor at the Federal University of Santa Catarina and one of the leading specialists in defense and cybernetics in Brazil. CEADI, is an important institution in Cape Verde, which receives funds from UNICEF and UNDP and has shown interest in working with topics related to artificial intelligence.

In view of the acceptance of two Spanish parliamentarians and one parliamentarian from Cape Verde, the methodology used was the Mini Focus Group and for logistical reasons of the very nature of the InterAgency Institute, as well as the debate having been promoted by parliamentarians from different countries and continents, the format went online.

Describe the advocacy activities carried out with this grant. What engagement did you have with parliamentarians, diplomats, officials, foreign ministers, etc?

We held a virtual meeting with the Organization of Iberoamerican States, Spain, in order to invite them to be our observer at the event. However, their presence cannot be confirmed, as on the same day they participated in the XXXIV Cumbre Hispano-Portuguesa to promote tools for schools in Portugal and Spain.

This advocacy was important when we detected that 22 Ibero-American presidents, including Portugal and Spain, adopted a communiqué asking for negotiations for the construction of a legal instrument that regulates the use of autonomous weapons. Such a proposal was presented and negotiated by Costa Rica.

There is an ongoing proposal to take the debate to Mozambique, Brazil, Angola and even Portugal. In Brazil, contact has been made with a legal commission that prepared a project presented to the Senate on the regulation of artificial intelligence. In Angola, Mozambique and Portugal, we have already mapped institutions interested in going deeper into the theme that could be bridges to raise the awareness of parliamentarians.

Although the Spanish parliamentarian Sonia Ferrer Tesoro was unable to participate on the day of the event, for personal reasons, we remain in contact to get answers from the parliamentarian on the issues addressed and the position of her party and the status of discussions on AI in the Spanish parliament.

In addition, there is an effort by the InterAgency Institute to take the discussion to other areas such as defense and education. We understand the importance of incorporating the discussion in schools so that the new generations can deal in the future and in the present in a more ethical and responsible way.

I highlight here the invitation made to the InterAgency Institute by a consultant in technologies in education in Brazil to participate in a training course for teachers. As well as the use of the Immoral Code documentary in classrooms that aim to promote debate among young people. Furthermore, we are also in contact with professors from Argentina, Italy, Peru and Portugal for the screening of the documentary.

What media and/or communications outputs did you have?

Before the event, two media insertions were made by Professor Sabrina Medeiros, who participated in interviews on the CNN network in Portugal, giving special emphasis to the issue of autonomous weapons regulation.

<https://cnnportugal.iol.pt/videos/cnn-sabado-15h56/636695210cf2ea367d571269>
(11/10/2022) Sabrina Medeiros from 10min and 20s

<https://cnnportugal.iol.pt/videos/cnn-sabado-13h56/636fcafa0cf255d6e13a12aa>
(11/12/2022) Sabrina Medeiros from 1min and 24s

We held an online event on the Zoom platform concomitantly with the screening of the documentary Immoral Code with the participation of parliamentarians and observers, which can be found at the following link <https://youtu.be/097qIXGk4xA>

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The Researchers Ana Paula Rodriguez and Juliana Martins submitted a project to the Campaign of the "Stop Killer Robots" (SKR) and got accepted. The activities will happen between October and March and, this time, the InterAgency Institute (IA) will promote an interparliamentary debate with Portugal and Spain, aiming to highlight the campaign in the Iberophony.

As Pesquisadoras Ana Paula Rodriguez e Juliana Martins submeteram projeto à Campanha "Stop Killer Robots" e foram contempladas. As atividades ocorrerão entre os meses de outubro à março e, desta vez, o InterAgency Institute (IA) fará um debate interparlamentar entre Portugal e Espanha, com o objetivo de dar voz à campanha na Iberofonia.

#stopkillerrobots #portugal #spain #iberophony #localdevelopment

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A partner institution through the #StopKillerRobots Campaign, the "Ibero Iakana Peace e Disarm", has been promoting a group of local events to request states to ratify the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW), whereas nuclear power politics is challenging the viability of these commitments.

We are learning from them how to achieve parliamentarians to sensibly inform on how middle and small states can have an important public role on those discussions.

Our parliamentary pledge on the Stop Killer Robots is been dedicated to the Portuguese-Spanish representatives and there is still a lot to progress.

Juliana Martins and Ana Paula Rodriguez are driving the initiative and Sabrina Medeiros was in fact this week to field work.

It is, then, an effort that gathers the Local and the Global Research Areas from our Institute!

Read more about it at: <https://iinkd.in/ibofKd>

#iinkd #local #iberofonia #parliamentarians #advocacy #global

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The Research Lead Ana Beatriz Duarte represented the InterAgency Institute (IA) in the last Paris Peace Forum (November, Geneva) in the panel "South-South Cooperation in Cyber Capacity Building and Good Practices". The panel statement focused on the need of cooperation in cyber capacity building, the role of the civil society, the importance of human rights prevalence and the perspective of IA as a think tank with Researchers from the Global South.

A Pesquisadora Líder Ana Beatriz Duarte representou o InterAgency Institute (IA) no último Paris Peace Forum (Novembro, Genebra), no painel "South-South Cooperation in Cyber Capacity Building and Good Practices". Sua fala inicial focou na necessidade de cooperação na construção de capacidades cibernéticas, o papel da sociedade civil, a importância da prevalência dos Direitos Humanos e a perspectiva do IA como think tank formado por Pesquisadores oriundos do Sul Global.

The event is available at/O evento está disponível em:
<https://iinkd.in/64-76b>

#paripeaceforum #southsouthcooperation #capacitybuilding #cyber #civilsociety #humanrights

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The event takes place within the scope of the Stop Killer Robots Campaign, with the aim of spreading awareness about the prohibition and/or regulation of lethal autonomous weapons that may affect human beings.

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[1st Interparliamentary Debate on AI]

This will be the pilot project of a series of interparliamentary focus groups that we will carry out with countries from the Spanish and Portuguese-speaking universe, foreseeing a series of audiovisual productions in these languages with the aim of promoting the inclusion of third countries in the international debate on the laws.

The predominance of debates in English has been an obstacle to understanding the theme that involves everyone as humanity. In this sense, giving a diverse voice (and language) to the debate means democratizing information, generating participation, promoting new points of view, including new social actors, enabling solutions and possibilities to weave, more and more, a culture of peace between countries Iberian descendants.

Watch the full event at: <https://iinkd.in/4KVZicXB>

ArtificialIntelligence #i #inteligenciartificial
#iberofonia #iberophony #ia

Ana Paula Rodriguez
Danielle Jacson Ayres Pinto
Luís C. Frietas
Juliana Miranda Martins

Ver tradução

1st Interparliamentary Debate on AI - 2 páginas

Describe how your project activities helped to influence and improve your government's policy position (for national grants), influence the region (for regional grants), and/or engage targeted communities (thematic). We seek brief stories of impact here.

During the period of activities of our project, we were able to sensitize the Organization of Ibero-American States which, despite not having participated as an observer in the debate, showed interest in going deeper and discussing the theme. The XXXIV Cumbre Hispano-Portuguesa shows us that it is a favorable environment for the InterAgency Institute to promote advocacy and dissemination of the campaign.

The approach and partnership with the Center for African Studies for Development and Innovation (CEADI), sensitized the Cape Verdean parliament to deepen the theme and the commitment to take the discussion to the parliament. Furthermore, during the debate, the Cape Verde parliamentarian exposed the technical difficulty of his country and took advantage of the debate to propose technical cooperation to the Spanish parliamentarian. This was a very positive asset of our debate.

After the event, Prof. Danielle Ayres, from the Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil, showed interest in taking both the documentary and actively participating in new interparliamentary debates, making herself available to InterAgency to establish the necessary bridges with the governments of Mozambique, Angola and Brazil. We point out that the aforementioned professor is one of Brazil's leading specialists in cybersecurity, which is why she was our observer at the event.

Furthermore, the InterAgency Institute is currently planning to partner with schools in the regions where our researchers are engaged, so that the topic of artificial intelligence is incorporated into discussions in education. We think of democratizing the broadening of the discussion to spaces where civil society can be heard and also guided about the effects of artificial intelligence on the ordinary lives of ordinary citizens.

What were the greatest strengths and/or successes of your project? Were there any set-backs?

The original project provided for the interparliamentary debate to take place between Portugal and Spain. From the mapping of the parliamentarians, we started to make the invitations from the first week of November. Taking into account that the parliamentary agenda is extensive, we decided to anticipate it so that guests could find availability.

On the part of Spain, we received confirmation from two parliamentarians: Sonia Ferrer Tesoro (PSOE) and Fernando Adolfo Gutiérrez Díaz de Otazu (PP). However, Portugal did not respond to our invitations, which were made 3 times. Faced with the lack of response and the time that was passing, we decided to keep the original idea of the project and focus on Iberophony. From the partnership with CEADI, we obtained the contact of the parliamentarian of Cape Verde, António Delgado Monteiro (UCID) who promptly agreed to participate

What was an initial difficulty soon turned into a great opportunity to engage Cape Verde in the campaign. In addition, the presence of a country from the Global South ensured that the debate was less Eurocentric and that the issue of economic and structural differences between the two countries was explored. The level at which they are in technological aspects is also very high, showing a gap between center and periphery.

On the one hand, Spain, which is the first country in the European Union to position itself alongside the European Commission for the construction of a normative framework consistent with the Community Regulation. On the other hand, Cape Verde, which is interested in the subject, but does not have the economic resources to undertake a technological update.

In this sense, one of the key points of the debate was the approach of the Cape Verde parliamentarian, who highlighted Spain as an old partner and requested technical cooperation for investment in new technologies and artificial intelligence, especially with regard to issues related to the sea. In this sense, a change in the strategy of our debate culminated in the creation of bridges and the possibility of cooperation between the invited countries.

Two women members of the Portuguese parliament (Claudia André (PSD) and Maria Emília Apolinário Sota Felicíssimo (PSD) responded to the invitation after the debate and they accepted the invitation to participate in a future interparliamentary debate

Describe how activities were used to engage with representatives from parliament, relevant government ministries, and/or diplomats.

After mapping the parliamentarians, we sent invitations with support material such as glossaries in the respective languages and Policy Briefs produced by the interAgency Institute on the subject, namely:

Glossary in Portuguese- <https://zenodo.org/record/6724980>

Glossary in Spanish - <https://zenodo.org/record/7610999>

Policy Brief - 5 pontos críticos para discutir LAWS
<https://zenodo.org/record/7046789>

Policy Brief - A multidimensional pledge for Stop Killer Robots
<https://zenodo.org/record/6371640>

Policy Brief - Um compromisso m multidimensional para Stop Killer Robots
<https://zenodo.org/record/6862962>

Policy Brief - Un compromiso multidimensional con Stop Killer Robots
<https://zenodo.org/record/6371638>

Over the months, we released the campaign Statements and produced 3 Policy Briefs specifically on the topic of our debate, namely:

Policy Brief - A ampliação do debate sobre a regulação das armas autônomas na Iberofonia <https://zenodo.org/record/7603288>

Policy Brief - La ampliación del debate sobre la regulación de las armas autónomas letales en la Iberofonia <https://zenodo.org/record/7603297>

Policy Brief - The expansion of the debate on the regulation of autonomous weapons in Iberophony <https://zenodo.org/record/7603479>

How did you seek to be inclusive and intersectional in implementing your project? What successes/challenges did you have? Please provide examples of your efforts to ensure gender and racial diversity (or other diversity).

Initially, we had thought of a balance between men and women when it came to holding the debate between Portugal and Spain. For this, we sought to invite parliamentarians who were part of the defense commissions, always respecting the number of existing women and sending invitations to men in equal numbers. In this way, with regard to Spain, we got a female parliamentarian and another male.

We also highlight that the parliamentarian Fernando Adolfo, from Spain, is a deputy for Melilla, a Spanish enclave in North Africa. The autonomous city of Melilla is a gateway for thousands of African migrants and refugees throughout the year. In June 2022, there was an incident in which police forces confronted people trying to jump over the wall that separates Spanish territory from Africa, leading to dozens of deaths.

We raised this issue because the InterAgency Institute monitors the situation of migrants and refugees around the world and fears the use of lethal weapons on moving populations, with the aim of carrying out border control. We elevate our discussion to include this vulnerable and marginalized part of the population.

However, with a change in strategy and the inclusion of Cape Verde, we were able to guarantee another diversity with regard to race by including a black parliamentarian. In addition, we guarantee geographic and economic diversity, as a priori there would be two European countries and now we were able to include the Global South and we had a more diverse debate, avoiding a Eurocentric debate.

Regarding the observers, we took into account issues of race and gender. The Cape Verde observer, Guedson Rompão, male and black. Brazilian observer Prof Danielle Ayres, female, white and LGBTQIA+. We also highlight that Professor Danielle represents a renowned specialist in the area of cybersecurity, an area mostly occupied by men.

What are your next steps, either to take the project further or build upon the work carried out from this grant?

Our next step is to do advocacy on these debate outcomes. Researcher Luís Campani will participate, on April 25th and 26th, in the Luxembourg Autonomous Weapons Systems Conference, where he will meet other members of the campaign and exchange experiences and results of the current round.

Researchers Sabrina Medeiros and Luís Campani had the paper “Killer Robots within the Lusophone Social Network: looking for interagency engagements” approved in the workshop “Multi-Level Governance and Interagency Cooperation Experiences to Build an Integrate Security,” at EWIS 2023, which will take place in Amsterdam in July 2023.

After the event, we had the return of two Portuguese parliamentarians who would like to participate in a new round. The two parliamentarians stressed the importance of the topic, but that at the time of the invitation they were involved in crises in Portugal's internal politics that were ordinarily on the agenda.

We are in contact, including sending the promotional support materials so that we can include them in the future. Professor Danielle Ayres showed interest in collaborating, putting us in direct contact with parliamentarians from Angola, Mozambique and Brazil

In addition, we adopt a strategy of permanent dissemination in schools and universities in order to deepen the topic of artificial intelligence and ethics from youth and thus stimulate interest in research that takes human rights and technological advancement into account.